

Integration of Artificial Intelligence in Mathematics Education: A Bibliometric Analysis

Abstract: Artificial Intelligence is a technological tool that is emerging as an effective tool for teaching and learning. It offers personalized assistance and can determine individual difficulties in learning. Due to its overwhelming popularity nowadays, many researchers have integrated AI into various fields, one of which is mathematics. To fill the gap in the lack of Filipino researchers that have employed a bibliometric analysis in this field, the researcher explored the academic field of AI integration in mathematics education. A bibliometric analysis was conducted on the publications indexed on the Scopus database, covering the period from January 2015 to June 2025. A total of 513 documents were identified and analyzed using VOS viewer. The United States and China are the top contributors to this field based on the number of documents affiliated with these countries. VOS viewer network visualization highlighted the terms "artificial intelligence" and "mathematics education" as the central themes connected to subtopics such as intelligent tutoring systems, generative AI, STEM, and ChatGPT.

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Article History:

Received Date : Feb 07, 2026
Revised Date : Mar 14, 2026
Accepted Date : Mar 14, 2026
Published Date : Mar 24, 2026

Keywords

Artificial Intelligence, Mathematics Education, Bibliometric Analysis.

1.Introduction

Artificial Intelligence or AI have emerged as powerful platforms for innovative approaches to teaching and learning in mathematics education, thus it is emerging as an effective tool at present (Stefanova & Georgiev, 2024). The AI technological tools is essential for a

wide range of technologies that can determine individual learning difficulties and provide personalized assistance to improve students' performance, as articulated by Kaushik et al. (2021). The incorporation of AI in mathematics educational setting has gained significant attention over the past few years and it focuses on the potential to address learning difficulties and enhance the practices on teaching. Mustafa (2024) stated that AI developments in mathematics instruction can operate to change established educational approaches by offering better tailored learning opportunities. This can improve student results and supports ongoing research and innovation within the field.

AI systems has an important aspect that can offer individualized educational support to learners, particularly in catering to their specific academic needs and advancing their performance levels (Hwang & Tu, 2021; Kaushik et al., 2021). Through the bibliometric analysis of Hwang and Tu (2021), it reveals the developments of AI implementation, research methods, tools, and technologies in mathematics education. AI tools is an important instrument that can offer advantageous opportunities, but one of the greatest challenges is that AI tools can also brings potential dangers that demand careful

evaluation (Stefanova and Georgiev, 2024). The different pedagogical models and innovative teaching strategies have contributed to reshaping mathematics teaching through practical and contextually relevant approaches (Cotic et al., 2024). The study of Cotic et al. 2024 identifies the emerging trends including the adoption of VR or virtual reality and AI that improves participation, interpretation of abstract principles, and provide student centered learning. Subroto et al. (2024) highlighted the increase of engagement in the use of artificial intelligence as a learning tool in mathematics education research. Recent research also shows that key trends include using AI as educational tools and methods. There is also growing interest in virtual reality, sustainable development, and COVID-19. These advancements are poised to significantly impact the future of mathematics education.

Many researchers have conducted rigorous analysis of the ongoing trends of AI in mathematics education that mainly focusing on the global scenario. However, to the best of our knowledge, it was found that there is a lack of Filipino researchers that have employed a bibliometric analysis to map the ongoing research trends that pertains to the application of AI in math education. To fill this gap, the researcher explored the current trends of studies within the scope of AI integration in math education.

This study aimed to present research data on scholarly works that are indexed on Scopus database from January 2015 to June 2025 about the integration of artificial intelligence in mathematics education, including scientific studies that tackle different dimensions of AI deployment on personalized learning, e-learning platforms, data-driven education, etc. Specifically, this study aimed to determine trends in publication about integration of AI in mathematics education in terms of number of publications per month and per year, top

publishing nations, influential authors, methodology utilized, types of indexed scholarly works, top journal sources; identify the key research topics related to AI integration in mathematics education; and assess the current status of research on AI integration in mathematics education in the Philippines, including the number of scholarly works published by Filipino authors. The selected timeframe is to cover the most recent publication to provide a timely data. This study used bibliometric analysis technique which aimed to quantify and analyze the data gathered to determine the volume and identify trends. The accessibility of bibliometric indicators and citation tracking through Scopus indexing has significant impact and influence of a journal (Santos et al., 2024).

This study provides a thorough analysis of how AI can be able to impacts mathematics educations that is significant in today's growing influence of AI. Analyzing the research trends on the application of AI to mathematics education is necessary for this study to give enlightenment about the potential benefits of using AI in learning mathematics that are valuable and would be helpful to researchers, including aspiring researchers, and it would serve as their foundations for future research. Exploring the field of AI integration in math education could also provide a comprehensive understanding that can be significant to educators and curriculum designers to enhance their teaching and method of instruction and to keep up with the current changes in the world of learning and technology. Additionally, these analyses would offer awareness of AI's impact in mathematics education, enabling policymakers to make informed decisions about research priorities and educational policies.

2. Literature Review

2.1. AI in Mathematics Education

Current studies in the field of AI integration into math education have shown that AI is becoming more significant in mathematical learning environments. AI can play a major role, especially in providing personalized learning, ongoing assessments, and better teaching methods to help solve problems in learning math (Hwang & Tu, 2021; Kaushik et al., 2021).

AI can reshape mathematics education by providing solutions to revolutionize teaching and learning difficulties. Rane (2024) stated that AI systems, including ChatGPT have the ability to provide adaptive lessons, instant feedback, and collaborative problem-solving features. AI can also determine what a student needs help with and support their progress (Hwang & Tu, 2021; Kaushik et al., 2021). Mathematics classes that utilize AI can increase student interest, encouraging constructive competition and adapting to different learning styles (Wardat et al., 2023). However, Rane (2023) noted that there are some problems with AI tools, such as the accuracy of solutions, the ability to fix biases, the ability to balance automation with human input, and concerns about data privacy. Wardel et al. (2024) noted that teachers feel extra pressure when using AI because it takes more effort than traditional teaching does. Despite these hurdles, AI has great potential for building enhanced learning spaces and cultivating students' critical thinking competencies (Rane, 2023; Hwang & Tu, 2021).

Panqueban and Huincahue (2024) argue that most current AI in math education studies is conducted through empirical and numerical methods. Interviews and questionnaires are the most frequently used data collection methods. To define the current state of research, the use of AI in terms of how it is used and how it should be done, as well as its role in teaching and learning, authors often apply systematic reviews as a method of assimilating the data

(Opesemowo & Adewuyi, 2024). They then underline trends such as the utilization of adaptive learning systems to enhance student performance and web-based evaluations. The potential for Sofia and Intelligent Tutoring Systems (ITS) was further tested with the ability to provide personalized support and solve tough math exercises. ChatGPT has the potential to be a popular online tool in the near future, given its relevance in education in the manufacturing age (Opesemowo & Adewuyi, 2024). Nonetheless, research in the field of young children and teacher training is lacking (Panqueban & Huincahue, 2024).

AI in math education was reviewed from 2013 to 2023 by Opesemowo and Adewuyi (2024), encompassing a total of 10 studies. They reported that the majority of studies were experiments (70%) that utilized qualitative procedures, 20% employed quantitative approaches, and 10% employed both. Questionnaires are the primary way of collecting information and are supported by interviews, eye-tracking experiments, and online formats; most questionnaires are applied by Opesemowo and Adewuyi (2024). The sample is as follows: participants differ, but most studies have researched different groups of teachers, students, postgraduates, and educators; however, the most typical groups are students and teachers. In terms of approaches, the most frequently used approach is coding/transcribing, followed by clustering; however, the highest percentage is represented by the other category. ChatGPT was the most commonly used AI tool and significantly surpassed the other categories with 20%. Internationally, AI is applied to the research of learning to math via observational material and numerical evidence. Intelligent tutoring systems facilitate learning; allow students to study, reach and help, and run notes; and benefit teachers during online assessments (Panqueban & Huincahue, 2024). The studies of Subroto et al. (2024) and Hwang and Tu (2021)

pertain to mathematical literacy, test-taking approaches, and AI gamification.

2.2. Bibliometric Analysis

To assess and classify bibliographic material in scientific fields, bibliometric analysis has become an important method (Lazarides et al., 2023). It uses statistical tools to examine academic papers, find influential authors, map collaboration networks, and identify research trends (Kumar, 2025). This approach has advanced substantially recently, with more bibliometric studies published over the past decade (Lazarides et al., 2023).

To examine scientific literature, bibliometric analysis is a systematic method that has the ability to determine patterns, trends, and impacts within research fields (Passas, 2024). According to Passas (2024), bibliometric analysis includes collecting data, scrutinizing, and applying diverse bibliometric techniques to generate meaningful knowledge. The efficiency of bibliometric analysis in analyzing large datasets and providing comprehensive overviews of research domains has gained popularity (Kumar, 2025). VOSviewer, CiteSpace, and Bibliometrix are some bibliometric tools that can offer diverse capabilities in visualizing and analyzing your data (Kumar, 2025). The methodologies of communication, economics, health, education, and other disciplines use bibliometrics (İri & Ünal, 2024). İri and Ünal (2024), in their analysis of 18, 432 publications from 1980 to 2023, reported that bibliometric analysis research is typically collaborative with a high collaborative index.

In the Philippines, nine hundred ninety-three scholarly works were identified and utilized for bibliometric analysis to determine trends in the field of research in mathematics education (Famulagan & Paylangco, 2024). While a decrease in research output over the last five

years has been illustrated, Famulagan and Paylangco (2024) revealed, in their analyses of Scopus-indexed articles from 2013-2023, a prominence in problem solving, teacher professional development, and the curriculum as the key focus area, with algebra, proof, and calculus receiving the most attention.

Several studies have employed this method to examine the role of AI in various fields, including maxillofacial fracture detection (Babu et al., 2024), security (Ilić et al., 2024), and education (Mayasari et al., 2024). There is increasing interest in AI concepts such as deep learning, machine learning, and security (Ilić et al., 2024). The rapid growth of AI uses has been shown in bibliometric studies, from medical diagnosis to educational tools (Babu et al., 2024; Mayasari et al., 2024). Through bibliometric analysis, we can identify leading countries, institutions, and researchers participating in specific fields, such as AI integration, in mathematics education-related studies (Ilić et al., 2024). Their work also provides research gaps and future directions, such as standardizing datasets, using AI in healthcare, and exploring AI in language and art education (Babu et al., 2024; Mayasari et al., 2024). For example, the growing popularity of content generated by AI tools and companies such as OpenAI is speeding up how AI can be used in education so that it does not hinder the critical thinking skills of students, with promises of personalized learning and smarter educational management (Ning et al., 2024). Many of the recently published studies indicate persistent attention to applying artificial intelligence in mathematical learning and broader educational contexts. The study shows annual growth in publication numbers, particularly in AI and mathematics education research which grows at an average rate of approximately 11.27%, according to Subroto et al., (2024). Studies in this domain are predominantly carried out by the United States, the United Kingdom, and China (Uzan et al., 2024; Subroto

et al., 2024). Present-day patterns involve incorporating AI into university-level education, educational tools, and subjects, including generative artificial intelligence and VR (Mayasari et al., 2024; Subroto et al., 2024). Research outcomes also suggest forthcoming study areas including boosting mathematical understanding, evaluation procedures, and the use AI tools in artistic learning (Subroto et al., 2024; Mayasari et al., 2024).

2.3. Theoretical Framework

Choosing which theoretical perspective will direct the research design and methodological procedures is a fundamental element of scholarly research. A well-constructed theoretical framework helps in interpreting new data, responding to future problems and guiding current research (Yasmin & Islam, 2021). Hence, this study is guided by Seymour Papert's constructionist theory. This concept stresses skill development through interactive technology use and purposeful self-directed activities. This technique requires students to program computers instead of computer programming students. It is connected in Piaget's constructivist principles.

Papert's constructionist model treats computers as core factors that can affect intellectual advancement and teaching methodologies. This theory can significantly intersect mathematics education with AI. This highlights the importance of children programming computers that are able to gain mastery over technology and engage in deep concepts of mathematics to enhance their problem solving skills. The theory's approach is consistent with the current agent, modeling, and abstraction of AI, especially in the cognitive modeling of mathematics education (Gadonis, 2017).

Recent publications indicate the increasing integration of artificial intelligence applications

in mathematical pedagogy through intelligent tutoring platforms and computerized testing frameworks (Panqueban & Huincahue, 2024). As Panqueban and Huncahue (2024) demonstrated in their study, there was a deficiency of academic research with regard to early childhood education and instructor preparation in this field. The perception of Papert as a groundbreaking approach to teachable mathematics has enabled thoughtfully designed computer applications, and it remains a source of motivation for scholars and teachers (Hoyles & Noss, 2017).

The theory of Papert's constructionism has a deep connection with AI; it rooted in the early days of Logo at MIT's AI Lab (Kahn & Winters, 2021). The continuing advancement of technology that merges machine learning capabilities with coding education platforms has encouraged this connection (Kahn & Winters, 2021). Additionally, Papert's research on electronic animal models for understanding human cognitive processes revealed historical links between constructionism and artificial intelligence (Hof, 2020).

Overall, modern applications of theory constructionism to AI and machine learning that emphasize a personalized approach are relevant projects that foster an understanding of cognitive processes and address critical issues such as algorithmic bias (Kafai & Morales-Navarro, 2024). By including AI and bringing together constructionist and postphenomenological standpoints, a framework for examining educational digital technologies can be developed (Wellner & Levin, 2023).

3. Methods

In this section, the researcher discussed the approach used to gather the appropriate and necessary data and information for the analysis. It includes the research design, locale

of the study, data source, data gathering procedure, and data analysis. The methodology of this study adapted similar methods applied by Famulagan and Paylangco (2024), who also employed bibliometric analysis to ensure the efficiency of the study conducted. The adapted methods were also aligned with the “bibliometric-systematic literature reviews” (B-SLR) framework suggested by Marzi et al. (2025) to increase the validity and reliability of the findings of the study.

3.1. Research Design

This study employed a quantitative descriptive research design. The collected information has been analyzed using bibliometric methods to identify patterns in the field of artificial intelligence applications in mathematical learning. The data examined can help determine publication trends over time, identify influential authors, and identify key research topics related to the integration of AI in math education.

3.2. Data Source

The dataset in the study focused on articles, conference papers, book chapters, and reviews that address AI in mathematics education published in the English language from January 2015 to June 2025 in the Scopus database. Nonempirical works such as editorials and opinion pieces, studies unrelated to AI or mathematics education, and duplicate publications were excluded. To eliminate potential biases, selection criteria were designed to create transparent guidelines in the screening process for every potential study. Table 1 shows the detailed inclusion and exclusion criteria that the researcher considered in the selection process.

Table 1 Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

INCLUSION CRITERIA	EXCLUSION CRITERIA
Articles, conference papers, book chapters, and reviews.	Nonempirical works (e.g., editorials, opinion pieces, letters, commentaries).
Focus on AI in mathematics education (e.g., AI tools, applications, methodologies).	Studies unrelated to AI or mathematics education (e.g., general pedagogy, non-AI tech).
Published in English.	Publications in languages other than English.
Empirical studies or systematic reviews.	Duplicate publications (e.g., same study in multiple journals/conference proceedings).
Directly addresses AI's role in mathematics education.	Indirect mentions of AI without substantive focus (e.g., brief references in broader contexts).
Articles published in Scopus-indexed journals from 2015 to June 2025.	Articles not indexed in Scopus or published outside the data range of 2015 to June 2025.

3.3. Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher of the study took several steps to gather the data. To conduct a bibliometric analysis, the researcher executed the data through intensive search via Boolean operators such as TITLE-ABS-KEY ("artificial intelligence" or "AI" or "machine learning" or "deep learning" or "generative AI" or "ChatGPT") and ("math* education" or "math* learning" or "STEM education" or "algebra teaching")) and PUBYEAR > 2014 and PUBYEAR < 2025 and (DOCTYPE("ar") or DOCTYPE("re")) and LANGUAGE("English"). The initial data gathered from the search results were included in the evaluation process to remove irrelevant data and duplicates via

Mendeley. Eligible works were then selected on the basis of the predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria in Table A. Relevant information such as title, publication year, author, methodology utilized, types of indexed scholarly works, and key findings was extracted for analysis.

As shown in Figure 1, a total of 5104 studies were initially retrieved from the Scopus database via Boolean operators such as "artificial intelligence" or "AI" and "mathematics education." After removing duplicates, 4885 scholarly works remained for further evaluation. From these, a total of 4372 studies were excluded: 61 were nonempirical, 3513 were unrelated to AI and mathematics education, 407 were nonEnglish works, and 391 were eliminated because they were outside the data range. After the studies were evaluated via the specified inclusion and exclusion criteria, a total of 513 scholarly works were retained for analysis (n=513). This number is approximately 9.2% lower than that reported in a previous study conducted by Subroto et al. (2024), which included 565 studies spanning a much longer period from 1986 to 2023. However, considering the timeframe, the present research covers a shorter and more recent period. This explains the difference in the study covered, which is why the number of included works is relatively close to that of the other studies, which span nearly four decades.

Fig 1. Flowchart of the inclusion and exclusion process

3.4. Data Analysis

The data collected were examined via bibliometric techniques. The study employed bibliometric analysis to track publication developments over time and pinpoint influential researchers utilizing tools such as VOSviewer. This study provides a statistical understanding of the research terrain and highlights important concentration areas. The monthly publication quantities, prevalence of different methodological types, and indexed scholarly publication categories were analyzed through Google Looker Studio. The citation metrics and data gathering were also performed via Harzing's Publish or Perish software. The aim of this study is to offer a thorough analysis of the present academic field concerning AI applications in mathematical learning. The results obtained by the researcher on these analyses were synthesized to present a holistic overview of the field while stressing the current status and future directions.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Trends in Publication about the Integration of AI in Mathematics Education

Fig 2. Monthly Distribution of Publications on AI in Mathematics Education (Jan 2015- June 2025)

Table 2 Yearly Distribution of Publications on AI in Mathematics Education (2015-JUNE 2025)

YEAR	RECORD COUNT
2025	130
2024	159
2023	60
2022	41
2021	30
2020	29
2019	12
2018	16
2017	14
2016	8
2015	14

The monthly distribution of publications on the integration of AI in mathematics education illustrates an upward trend, as shown in Figure 2. The graph shows a lower number of works published between 2015 and 2020. However, beginning in 2021, there was a gradual increase, followed by sharp growth from 2023 onward. In late 2024 and early 2025, the highest peaks recorded a monthly count of up to 28 publications, specifically in April 2025.

In connection with Figure 2, Table 2 shows the annual distribution of studies related to AI and mathematics education. The data revealed that

the number of research outputs was lower from 2015 to 2020, ranging between 8 and 29. A continuous increase was perceived in 2021 and 2022, with 30 and 41 studies published, respectively, followed by an increase in 2023, with 60 scholarly works. A spike in growth occurred in 2024, where 159 works were recorded, while the first half of 2025 already reached 130 studies.

The number of documents published from January 2015 to June 2025 had a monthly average of 4.07 or a 1.99% growth rate. From 2015-2024, the number of publications per year recorded an average of 38.1, or a 27.34% growth rate annually. This figure is more than double than of the previous study conducted by Subroto et al. (2024), with an average annual growth rate of 11.27%, which covers a longer period (1986-2023) with 565 documents. The faster growth rate observed in this study suggests that more scholarly works are being published in the Scopus database in a shorter period. This highlights the recent and stronger trend in the field. The review conducted by Panqueban and Huincahue (2024) confirms this increasing pattern and revealed a noticeable increase in research on AI-related mathematics education, with an analysis of 29 articles.

Table 3 Frequency Distribution of Top Publishing Countries

COUNTRY	NO. OF DOCUMENTS	NO. OF TOTAL LINK STRENGTH
United States	125	45
China	69	12
Malaysia	24	11
United Kingdom	21	22
Spain	20	14
South Africa	18	6
India	16	3
Austria	9	17

A total of 84 countries were identified that contributed to this field. Table 3 shows the list of the top countries by number of documents and link strength. The United States is leading with 125 publications, followed by China with 69 papers. Other country contributors include Malaysia (24), the United Kingdom (21), Spain (20), South Africa (18), India (16), and Austria (9).

In terms of their country collaboration strength, the United States is leading again, totaling a remarkable link strength of 45. This result illustrates its central role in international partnerships. The countries of the United Kingdom, Austria, and Spain follow with 22, 17, and 14, respectively. Norway and South Korea with a total number of 13 links, also have strong ties with the other nations, even though they have fewer publications. The data results indicate that research output does not always match collaboration levels. China (12) and Malaysia (11), for example, rank high in publications, but in terms of collaboration with other countries, they have weaker links. Moreover, Austria, with fewer papers has played a more active role in cooperation networks.

Fig 3. Country Collaboration Network Visualization (VOSviewer)

Using VOSviewer to create a map based on publication data with network visualization, as shown in Figure 3, helps show the activity of the top publishing countries. The nations with larger nodes indicate more active countries, such as the United States, China, and the United Kingdom. The thicker the lines between them are, the stronger the partnerships. The United States and China have the most publications, which matches with the findings of Subroto et al. (2024). These findings demonstrated that the US and China are leaders in terms of AI integration in math education research worldwide.

Table 4 Top 10 Authors Based on Citation Counts

Authors	Title	Affiliations	Cites
Wang Y.; Liu X.; Shi S.	Deep neural solver for math word problems	China	320
Wardat Y.; Tashtoush M.A.; AlAli R.; Jarrah A.M.	ChatGPT: A revolutionary tool for teaching and learning mathematics	United Arab Emirates; Oman; Jordan; Saudi Arabia	236
Hwang G.J.; Tu Y.F.	Roles and research trends of artificial intelligence in mathematics education: A bibliometric mapping analysis and systematic review	Taiwan	221
Sánchez-Ruiz L.M.; Moll-López S.; Nuñez-Pérez A.; Moraño-Fernández J.A.; Vega-Fleitas E.	ChatGPT Challenges Blended Learning Methodologies in Engineering Education: A Case Study in Mathematics	Spain	130

Sung W.; Ahn J.; Black J. B.	Introducing Computational Thinking to Young Learners: Practicing Computational Perspectives Through Embodiment in Mathematics Education	United States	122
Wang L.; Zhang D.; Gao L.; Song J.; Guo L.; Shen H. T.	MathDQN: Solving arithmetic word problems via deep reinforcement learning	China	100
Lee I.; Perret B.	Preparing High School Teachers to Integrate AI Methods into STEM Classrooms	United States	88
Lee D.; Yeo S.	Developing an AI-based chatbot for practicing responsive teaching in mathematics	United States	88
How M.L.; Hung W.L.D.	Educating AI-thinking in science, technology, engineering, arts, and mathematics (STEAM) education	Singapore	87
Botana F.; Hohenwarter M.; Janicic P.; Kovács Z.; Petrovic I.; Recio t.; Weitzhofer S.	Automated Theorem Proving in GeoGebra: Current Achievements	Spain; Austria; Serbia;	84

Table 4 shows individuals whose works gained the most recognition in the field on the basis of what is reflected in their citation counts. Wang et al. (2017) are authors from China rank first, receiving 320 citations for their study on deep neural solvers for math word problems, which established their work as a highly influential contribution to AI integration in mathematics education. The following is the scholarly work of Wardat et al. (2023) from the United Arab Emirates, Oman, Jordan, and Saudi Arabia, which obtained 236 citations for their research via the ChatGPT. This shows the strong relevance of AI applications in mathematics education. Hwang and Tu (2021) from Taiwan also made a significant impact on their study with 221 citations through their systematic review related to AI and math education. Among other researchers, their study helps contribute knowledge to what AI can do and its potential to have an impact on the mathematics education research field.

AI has the potential to enhance teaching methodologies and improve student

engagement by facilitating understanding of complex mathematical concepts in mathematics education (Borah & Borah, 2024). Studies related to the integration of AI into mathematics education have gained significant influence, but challenges exist in their accessibility. The analysis of the research methods used in the studies shows a varied distribution across the different approaches.

Fig 4. Types of Research Methodologies Employed

As shown in the chart in Figure 4, more than half of the documents (53.4%) are marked as N/A (not applicable) because of limited access to the Scopus database, which stops the retrieval of detailed method information from some publications. Among those with available data, 16.4% used a quantitative research method. Quantitative research designs collect data via structured methods such as surveys, experiments, interviews, observations, and records, using tools such as structured questionnaires, Likert scales, and semantic questionnaires (Permatasari et al., 2025). Moreover, 15.8% of the studies employed qualitative designs. The main types of qualitative research designs include narrative, grounded theory, phenomenological, case study, and ethnographic approaches (Oranga & Matere, 2023). Finally, 14.4% employ mixed-method research. Mixed methods research is a combination of quantitative and qualitative data within a single study to address complex research questions that cannot be fully answered by either approach alone (Sharma et al., 2023).

The methodologies employed in the studies reveals that 274 out of 513 documents are not applicable. Among the specified methodologies, quantitative research was the most prevalent with 84 occurrences, followed by qualitative research, with 81 counts. Moreover, 74 of the studies employed mixed-method research. This suggests that quantitative research is dominant, indicating that researchers in this field prefer more numerical data and statistical analysis. Qualitative research is also well represented, highlighting the importance of an in-depth understanding of qualitative data. Mixed-method research is also used by a significant number of studies, indicating the effectiveness of combining quantitative and qualitative approaches.

This distribution shows that while there are different methods used in the Field, research on limited access challenges reveals a variety of impacts in different settings. In conducting field research, limited access to the chosen database can impact both data gathering processes and methodological decisions, necessitating that researchers employ flexible tactics to preserve study reliability (Amano et al., 2022). Therefore, according to Famulagan and Paylangco (2024), publishing in open-access journals can help make research more accessible and increase citations.

Table 5 Frequency Distribution of Document Types

	TYPE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
1	ARTICLE	246	47.95%
2	CONFERENCE PAPER	223	43.47%
3	BOOK CHAPTER	32	6.24%
4	REVIEW	12	2.34%

The different types of scholarly works, such as articles, conference papers, book chapters, and reviews, are presented in Table 1.5. Articles constitute the largest part, with 246 documents or 47.95% of the total 513 studies. The number of conference papers follows 43.47%, totaling 223 works. A total of 32 studies, or 6.24% were recorded in book chapters. Finally, 12 review articles were recorded, accounting for 2.34% of the total studies included in the analysis.

Journal articles with a large number of document types indicate that researchers prefer journals as the primary platform (Subroto et al. 2024) for sharing comprehensive studies and for advancing scholarly discourse. The conference papers following the journal articles with high number of works highlight the

vibrant and evolving landscape of scientific research. This result shows that researchers also prefer to share preliminary findings, swap ideas, and gather feedback before moving on to journal publications. The articles and conference papers dominating the research field of AI in mathematics learning highlight the importance of both formal journal dissemination and active engagement in academic conferences, which are crucial for enhancing the visibility of research on integrating AI into mathematics education.

Table 6 Top Journal Sources based on the Number of Documents

Name of Journal	Number of Documents
Lecture Notes in Computer Science Including Subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics	27
Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems	13
Sustainability Switzerland	12
ACM International Conference Proceeding Series	11
Communications in Computer and Information Science	10
International Journal of Artificial Intelligence in Education	8
Education Sciences	8
Eurasia Journal of Mathematics Science and Technology Education	8
International Electronic Journal of Mathematics Education	8
IEEE Global Engineering Education Conference Educon	8

Table 6 shows the top journal sources from the Scopus database on the basis of the number of documents published related to the integration of AI in mathematics education. A journal from Springer named Lecture Notes in Computer Science including Subseries Lecture in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics, is leading with a total of 27 documents. This is followed by Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems, Sustainability Switzerland, and ACM International Conference Proceeding Series, with total numbers of 13,12, and 11, respectively. Other journal sources include Communications in Computer and Information Science (10), the International Journal of Artificial Intelligence in Education (8), Educational Sciences (8), the Eurasia Journal of Mathematics Science and Technology Education (8), the International Electronic Journal of Mathematics Education (8), and the IEEE Global Engineering Education Conference Educon (8).

Research journals are crucial for disseminating a validated knowledge, established credibility, preserve scholarly works, foster academic dialogue, and career advancement by providing a rigorous, peer-reviewed platform for researchers to share discoveries, fill the gaps and build on existing work, and contribute to educational progress especially on AI integration in mathematics education.

4.2. Key Research Topics Related to AI Integration in Mathematics Education

The continuous increase in researchers' interest in AI-related research in mathematics education has led to an increasing number of studies that examine different research subjects. VOSviewer was utilized to develop a text data map to illustrate the relevant research topics in this field. It focuses on the co-occurrence of keywords across the dataset via the network visualization mode. A total of 1450 unique terms were found through the analysis.

To make the visualization significant, a minimum threshold of 10 occurrences was applied to ensure that only relevant terms were included and to highlight the dominant and recurring themes that truly shaped the field of AI integration in mathematics education.

Fig 5. Keyword Co-Occurrence Network Visualization of Research on AI in Mathematics Education Using VOSviewer

The terms are divided into two clusters within the analysis, as shown in Figure 5, indicating that they are distinct but that both of the clusters are related. The red cluster emphasizes the terms mathematics education, artificial intelligence, and ChatGPT. Strong linkages exist between the terms case study, impact, intelligent tutoring system, and STEM education. This implies that many studies have focused on the classroom-level application of AI, which uses ChatGPT and other intelligent systems, to examine different classroom-based challenges through case studies and assess their effects on teaching practices, the learning of students, and educational outcomes. The result correspond with those of Opemesowo and Adewuyi (2024), who noted that ChatGPT is developing into a major AI instrument for mathematics education, and according to Ning et al. (2022), interest in how AI tools can improve problem-solving abilities, provide individualized responses, and support mathematical curriculum advancement has increased.

On the other hand, green cluster is formed with the terms engineering, STEM, and technology.

This demonstrates that a more multifaceted position and where AI integration in mathematics education can be explored in connection with a wider technological and scientific area of descent. The appearance of STEM and engineering in this cluster indicates that AI can reshape the mathematical learning of students by solving long standing pedagogical problems and preparing them for future demands. The results obtained from the analysis align with those of other studies, as stated by Mustafa (2024), AI-powered adaptive learning technologies and intelligent tutoring systems can help provide personalized learning experiences that allow students to progress at their own pace while receiving immediate feedback. These kinds of systems analyze the learner's activity data to consistently develop the instructional practices that lead to academic success. These findings indicate that incorporating AI allows for adaptive identification of learning deficits and increases the performance of students in mathematical studies (Hwang & Tu, 2021).

Fig 6. Overlay Visualization of Keyword Co-Occurrences

The overlay visualization in VOSviewer is shown in Figure 6, which illustrates how the research topic in this field has evolved over time. The transition of colors from purple in earlier publications to yellow highlights more recent work in this field. AI and mathematics education are represented in green, which illustrates that these areas are consistently explored throughout the period covered in this

analysis. The map also revealed the rise of new topics such as ChatGPT and generative artificial intelligence which are marked in yellow. The illustration shows the shift in interest in research topics, particularly from 2023-2024, in which AI tools became more integrated into educational environments. The impact of intelligent tutoring systems was at the forefront in earlier years but it was gradually overshadowed by newer concepts. The changes seen reflect that a broader trend in research is evolving from traditional applications such as tutoring systems to more interactive and adaptive generative tools. There has also been a noticeable increase in attention given to emerging technologies such as ChatGPT and generative AI as research on AI in mathematics continues to expand. These results align with the findings of Opesemowo and Adewuyi (2024), who highlighted ChatGPT as the leading AI tool in mathematics education, underscoring its potential to help bridge educational gaps in the era of the Fourth Industrial Revolution.

Table 7 Top Keywords Based on the Number of Occurrences

TERM	OCCURENCES
Artificial intelligence	76
Chatgpt	55

mathematics education	48
stem education	34
Technology	30
Science	21
Impact	16
Engineering	15

Table 7 lists the top keyword terms ranked on the basis of their number of occurrences. The leading term in the list is artificial intelligence with 76 occurring, followed closely by the term ChatGPT at 55, and followed by mathematics education, with a total of 48 occurring. Other relevant terms are stem education (34), technology (30), science (21), impact (16), and engineering (15). The results highlight the most commonly discussed topics, which are artificial intelligence, ChatGPT, and mathematics education. Additionally, other related keywords, such as GeoGebra, statistics, tutoring, intelligent tutoring systems, COVID, and problem-solving have also been identified. This result demonstrates that the use of AI tools is versatile and can be applied across various areas of mathematics that can offer personalized learning experiences.

4.3. Current Research Status of Research on AI in Mathematics Education in the Philippines

Table 8 Summary of AI-related Mathematics Education Research in the Philippines (Scopus Database)

	Authors	Title	Year Published	Type	No. of Citation
1	Inoferio et al.	Coping with math anxiety and lack of confidence through AI-assisted Learning	2024	Article	45
2	Remoto J.P.	ChatGPT and other AIs: Personal relief and limitations among mathematics-oriented learners	2024	Article	13
3	Del Mundo et al.	Discourse analysis on experience-based position of science, mathematics, and Tech-Voc educators on generative AI and academic integrity	2024	Article	11

4	Canonigo A.M.	Levering AI to enhance students' conceptual understanding and confidence in mathematics	2024	Article	5
5	Barrientos et al.	Discourse analysis on academic integrity generative AI: Perspectives from science and mathematics students in higher education	2024	Article	3
6	Alvarez J.I.	EVALUATING THE IMPACT OF AI-POWERED TUTORS MATHGPT AND FLEXI 2.0 IN ENHANCING CALCULUS LEARNING	2024	Article	3
7	Aborot et al.	Gul.ai: AI- and IoT-enabled Plant-growing System for Boosting STEM Education in the Philippines	2022	Conference Paper	3
8	Buniel et al.	Modeling the influence of AI dependence to research productivity among STEM undergraduate students: case of a state university in the Philippines	2025	Article	0
9	Ballenas E. B. and Lasco M. T.	Exploring Mathematics Teachers' Behavioral Intentions to Use Artificial Intelligence Through Structural Equation Modeling	2024	Conference Paper	0
10	Garcia et al.	Engineering students' perceptions and actual use of AI-based math tools for solving mathematical problems	2025	Article	0
11	Etcuban J. O.	The use of ChatGPT in addressing Algebra anxiety and promoting confidence	2025	Article	0

The current status of the Philippines in the field of AI and mathematics education is still in its emerging stage, but it is gaining increasing attention from Filipino researchers. Most of the studies identified are recent, as shown in Table 8, which shows that AI in education is a new but rapidly developing field in the country. These studies were published between 2022 and 2025.

Among the 513 documents included in the analysis, only 11 are affiliated with the Philippines. While AI in mathematics education is still emerging, there is already a visible and growing interest in integrating AI into mathematics teaching and learning in the country. Among the identified authors, Inoferio et al. (2024) are the leading contributors, with 45 citations for their work that addresses math

anxiety and a lack of confidence through AI-assisted learning. Articles and conference papers are the only types of scholarly works identified, with record counts of 9 and 2, respectively. However, compared with the overall 993 mathematics publications in the Philippines identified by Famulagan and Paylangco (2024), the 11 scholarly works related to AI in math education demonstrate a limited integration of AI into the Philippine mathematics education research topics. Nevertheless, the fact that most of these works have already received a significant number of citations indicates that the Philippine's contributions have the potential to have an impact.

5. Conclusion

Research on the integration of artificial intelligence in mathematics education has experienced sustained growth over the past decade, illustrating the importance and impact of AI in improving educational practices, especially in mathematics. This discipline is centered on the developed and knowledge-driven countries, with the United States and China leading, whereas developing countries, such as the Philippines, remain underrepresented. In strengthening the research impact, an international partnership is highly recommended to develop more collaborations. Well-made research from top authors demonstrates the importance of research productivity, engagement, and citation impact in shaping the academic landscape in the use of AI for teaching and learning. The analysis of keywords through network and overlay visualization via VOSviewer reveals that the field is evolving and progressing toward innovative applications of AI, such as generative AI, adaptive learning systems, and AI-powered assessment. While the number of research outputs in the Philippines remains limited, since it covers only scholarly works indexed in the Scopus database, it shows signs of scholarly potential on the basis of its citation impact.

In view of the results of the study, the researcher recommends the following: a conduct of study that goes beyond foundational application and explores emerging AI tools other than ChatGPT; a conduct of Bibliometric Analysis to other databases, such as PubMed, Web of Science, Google Scholar, etc., to get a wider insight on the status of AI integration in Mathematics Education related studies; institutions should provide more training and seminars on other research methodologies in research writing to enable researchers to contribute more actively to global discourse; researchers should publish in open-access journals to increase the

visibility, accessibility, and citation counts of their studies; and for a Filipino researcher, it is encouraged to conduct studies that aim to address local challenges in mathematics education through AI.

Conflict of Interest. The authors declare there is no conflict of interest

Funding.

The project received no funding from the government, organisations, or institutions. Authors sponsored this project.

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